

An Economic Value of Remote Sensing Information:
application to agricultural production and maintaining ground water quality

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General considerations for research

Central Hypothesis:

- Regional resource management can be improved and public health maintained by coupling MRLI with agricultural, geospatial, and hydrogeologic models, which allows estimation of the value of information (VOI) for MRLI and Landsat**
- Landsat user survey (Miller et al. 2011) identified environmental science and management applications (40 percent), water use and land cover (27 percent), planning and development (11 percent), the agricultural sector (8 percent) as top 4 application areas.
 - At a global scale, the remote sensing information (MRLI) facilitates spatiotemporal analysis of the public good of groundwater resources to estimate the value of information (VOI) for MRLI and Landsat.
 - MRLI provides the population of land uses, while traditional techniques focus on only a sample of land uses or a lower quality of information.
 - Estimates of value are critical because nonpoint pollution accumulates from nonpoint sources over a period of time.
 - Approximately 80 percent of lowans depend on groundwater for their drinking water so the regulation of nitrate contamination is an important issue.

Outline of presentation

- Conceptual framework and background
- Case Study overview and Landsat/MRLI data
- Models and results
- Remote sensing value of Information (VOI) estimates
- Future work, summary, and acknowledgements

Integrated assessment approach

VOI is benefit possible with information minus benefit possible without it:

$$VOI_{\omega}(t) = B_{\omega}(t) - B_{\omega}(0)$$

General economic model:

$$\max_R PQ$$

$$s.t. \text{ risks} \leq \alpha$$

P = price of relevant crops
Q = aggregation of producer outputs
 α = represents the probability exceeding a regulatory standard that causes groundwater quality to be a public health risk.
R = vector of regulations.

Cumulative Nitrate Indicator results

Variables	Area Coefficients	Leached Quantity Coefficients
Lag1 (change in measured NO ₃ from previous year)	0.08 (0.736)	0.24 (0.200)
Capture Zone 1	2.28 (0.046)	0.77 (0.000)
Capture Zone 2	5.88 (0.014)	3.59 (0.000)
Capture Zone 3	1.71 (0.018)	1.88 (0.000)
Capture Zone 4 to 10	0.10 (0.164)	0.04 (0.000)
Quaternary thickness	-0.47 (0.007)	-0.74 (0.000)

Note: () = p-value

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Probability of well survival (G) result

N = 18, 615

Variable	Parameter	Estimate
Depth (m)	B_1	-0.0087 (0.0001)
Time trend (days)	β_2	-0.00022 (0.00002)
*		
Year 1	γ_1	-3.601 (0.056)
Year 2	γ_2	-3.264 (0.035)
Year 3	γ_3	-3.108 (0.018)
Year 4	γ_4	-3.033 (0.013)
Year 5	γ_5	-2.988 (0.010)
Year 6	γ_6	-2.968 (0.007)
Year 7	γ_7	-2.958 (0.005)

* = 603 sub-basin indicator variables omitted for clarity
 () = standard error

Optimal versus realistic

- The VOI estimates are an optimal solution to a benefit maximization problem with one constraint (i.e. EPA MCL).
- Existing policies are taken as a given, bundled set.
- Likely reduction in VOI estimates with particular land use policies:
 - Mandated requirements of Renewable Fuel Standards
 - Farm bill direct subsidies and changing commodity program payments
 - USDA / NRCS programs to maintain fallow lands
 - Incentives to limit fertilizer application in vulnerable well catchment zones
 - Land use planning and zoning restrictions in vulnerable watersheds

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Future Work

- Increased realism and policy analysis
- Finer-scale analysis of land management practices
 - e.g. nitrate uptake by vegetation, efficacy of riparian buffer zones, nitrogen loading by livestock, influence on flowpaths by berms and tile drain system
- Decision support system and scenarios
 - e.g. drill new production wells, change MCL thresholds, alter LULC pattern and agricultural production, change well production levels
- Extend Landsat-derived LULC back beyond 2000
- Additional ecosystem services
 - e.g. more agricultural commodities, surface water quality, habitat provision
 - Improvements to hydrogeologic models
 - e.g. develop MODFLOW model, incorporate denitrification at depth, obtain 3D structure of lithology
 - Increased extent/alternate locations

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Summary

- This application would not be possible without MRLI, and VOI cannot be estimated without an application.
- An estimate of VOI for MRLI and the Landsat Data Continuity Mission is \$38.1B ± \$8.8B for northeastern Iowa.
- VOI estimate could be lower with additional constraints, land use policies, and management practices.
- VOI estimate could be higher with larger regions or different applications.
- By soft-coupling complex geospatial, agricultural production, hydrogeologic and groundwater vulnerability models, our results give regional decision makers natural resource management tools to use in context of protecting public health.

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*Something to watch over us:
the Earth should be monitored more carefully*

"Long-term measurements will allow researchers to get a reliable grip on the science of climate change and other environmental stresses. A firm grasp of the basic trends is a necessary precondition for understanding and for informed policy."

"The number of civilian Earth-observing satellites flown by the United States government looks likely to fall from 23 today to just six in 2020, and the number of instruments in orbit could drop from 90 to 20."

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